

Dynamic analysis of the evolution law of low-velocity impact damage in composite laminates with a continuum damage model

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Abstract:

In this paper, a numerical method for the evaluation of composite laminates damage under the low-velocity impact was proposed based on the continuum damage mechanics (CDM) and the cohesive zone model (CZM). **The intra-ply damage including matrix crack and fiber fracture was represented by the constitutive model which took into account the physical progressive failure behavior using the damage variable.** The delamination at the interface between plies was characterized by the CZM which took into account the normal crack and the tangent slip using a relation between stress and displacement. The FEM which combined the CDM and CZM brought stable simulations, overcoming the numerical instability for the simulation of the composite laminates damage under impact. It can effectively establish the relation between the mesoscale structure and the macroscopical response under impact. The effect of interlaminar toughness on the impact damage was investigated, which has not been thoroughly discussed in most literature as yet. The numerical prediction has a good agreement with the experimental test.

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